

Association Between Infantile Colic and Development of Childhood Functional and Atopic Disorders: A Multicentric Case Control Study

Bhaswati C Acharyya¹, Sundaram Balasubramanian², Sandipan Dhar³, Swapan Mukherjee⁴, Pramod Jog⁵, Vidyut Bhatia⁶, Krishna Chaitanya Veligandla⁷, Bhavesh Kotak⁷, Rahul Rathod⁷, Ashley George Soares⁷, Sourabh Bharat Sonawale⁷, Seema Vikas Bhagath⁷, Sushma Jayan⁸, Manipa Saha⁸, Monjori Mitra^{9*}

¹Department of Pediatric Gastroenterology, Institute of Child Health, Kolkata, West Bengal, India

²Department of Pediatrics, Kanchi Kamakoti Childs Trust Hospital, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India

³Department of Pediatric Dermatology, Institute of Child Health, Kolkata, West Bengal, India

⁴Department of Pediatric Neurology, Institute of Child Health, Kolkata, West Bengal, India

⁵Medipoint Hospital, Pune, Maharashtra, India

⁶Department of Pediatrics, Max Superspeciality Hospital, New Delhi, India

⁷Medical Affairs, Global Generics India, Dr. Reddy's Laboratories Limited, Hyderabad, Telangana, India

⁸Medical Affairs, Medclin Research Pvt. Ltd., Kolkata, West Bengal, India

⁹Department of Pediatrics, Institute of Child Health, Kolkata, West Bengal, India

Citation: Bhaswati C Acharyya, Sundaram Balasubramanian, Sandipan Dhar, Swapan Mukherjee, Pramod Jog, Monjori Mitra, et al. Association Between Infantile Colic and Development of Childhood Functional and Atopic Disorders: A Multicentric Case Control Study. *Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour.* 2023;2(16):1-12.

Received Date: 17 October, 2023; **Accepted Date:** 25 October, 2023; **Published Date:** 27 October, 2023

***Corresponding author:** Monjori Mitra, Department of Pediatrics, Institute of Child Health, Kolkata, West Bengal, India

Copyright: © Monjori Mitra, Open Access 2023. This article, published in *Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour (ICMCRJ)* (Attribution 4.0 International), as described by <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

ABSTRACT

Aims: The study aimed to check the association between infantile colic and childhood disorders namely allergic rhinitis/asthma, atopic dermatitis, migraine, and functional abdominal pain-not otherwise specified (FAP-NOS) in Indian children

Methods: Children aged 2-18 years diagnosed with allergic rhinitis/asthma, atopic dermatitis, childhood migraine, or FAP-NOS were enrolled as cases, and age-matched healthy children as controls. Data on infantile colic was collected using a structured questionnaire derived from the ROME IV diagnostic criteria.

Results: A total of 300 cases and 100 age-matched controls were included in the study. A significant association was noted between controls and cases with a history of infantile colic (OR=2.94, p=0.0017). Significant association was also observed between each of the four disorders and infantile colic: allergic rhinitis (OR=3.14, p=0.0052) and

atopic dermatitis (OR=3.14, p=0.005) were found to have a stronger association compared to childhood migraine (OR=2.94, p=0.0089) and FAP-NOS (OR=2.55, p=0.025). Using univariate analysis, gestational age (<37 weeks) in atopic dermatitis, C-section delivery in allergic rhinitis and childhood migraine, and mixed type of feed (breastmilk and formula feed) in FAP-NOS were detected as independent risk factors (p<0.05) in the association of the specific diseases with infantile colic. Multivariate regression analysis showed that the association of infantile colic with childhood migraine and FAP-NOS was affected by type of feed and type of delivery, respectively.

Conclusion: Infantile colic is significantly associated with childhood disorders namely allergic rhinitis, atopic dermatitis, childhood migraine, and FAP-NOS.

Keywords: Colicky pain; Allergic rhinitis; Atopic dermatitis; Childhood migraine; Functional Abdominal Pain-Not Otherwise Specified (FAP-NOS)

INTRODUCTION

Infantile colic is a commonly encountered phenomenon of excessive and inconsolable crying in infants, who are otherwise healthy with no obvious diagnosis of any disorder. Although self-resolving and benign, infantile colic causes distress to parents and caregivers, which is often the deterministic criteria for infantile colic. In fact, infantile colic is defined as per ROME IV as 'an infant who is less than 5 months of age when the symptoms start and stop; recurrent and prolonged periods of infant crying, fussing, or irritability reported by caregivers that occur without obvious cause and cannot be prevented or resolved by caregivers; no evidence of infant failure to thrive, fever, or illness'.^[1-2]

The prevalence of infantile colic is considered as 20%; potential etiologic factors that have been suggested to be causative include psychosocial factors, neurodevelopmental features, dysbiosis of gut microbiota, early life events, gastrointestinal motility, and type of feed.^[1] Nevertheless, the most well-accepted theory currently is that infantile colic is one of the foremost disorders in infants caused by dysbiosis.^[1,3,4] Earlier studies demonstrated infantile colic to be associated with other diseases in which dysbiosis is thought to play a role, such as allergic disorders, atopic diseases,^[5-7] childhood migraine,^[8-10] and recurrent abdominal pain.^[7] However, there is scarcity of studies in the Indian population that have investigated any such association. The current study was planned to explore whether there is any association of infantile colic with other disorders that manifest later in life in Indian children. Furthermore, in a recent study, a higher incidence of infantile colic was shown in infants who were mixed- or formula-fed (odds ratio, OR = 3.0, 95% CI [1.3, 7.2], p = 0.012).^[11] However, there is a dearth of data on the role of several other factors that are also known to affect gut microbiome in children^[12] and their effect, if any, on the association of infantile colic and childhood diseases. Therefore, we investigated if factors such as gestational age, weight at birth, type of delivery, and type of feed were independent risk factors in the association of infantile colic and the childhood diseases being investigated in this study: allergic rhinitis/asthma, atopic dermatitis, childhood migraine, or Functional Abdominal Pain-Not Otherwise Specified (FAP-NOS).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This was a multicentric, case-control study conducted to evaluate the association between infantile colic and common childhood disorders namely allergic rhinitis/asthma, atopic dermatitis, childhood migraine, and FAP-NOS. Participants in the age group of 2-18 years with a confirmed diagnosis of allergic rhinitis/asthma, atopic dermatitis, childhood migraine, or FAP-NOS (as per the age group applicable to each condition) were enrolled as cases. Diagnosis was based on standard criteria: allergic rhinitis/asthma based on ARIA guidelines,^[13] atopic dermatitis based on Hanifin and Rajka criteria,^[14] childhood migraine based on ICHD Edition 3 guideline,^[15] and FAP-NOS based on ROME IV criteria.^[1] Healthy participants in the age group of 2-18 years demographically matched to the cases were enrolled as controls. Patients with a history of any chronic illness, neurological conditions affecting gut motility, or endocrine disorders including type I diabetes mellitus, hypothyroidism, or obesity were excluded from the study.

Ethical committee approval was obtained from the four participating tertiary hospitals namely Institute of Child Health (Kolkata), Kanchi Kamakoti Childs Trust Hospital (Chennai), Medipoint Hospital (Pune), and Max Super Speciality Hospital (New Delhi). Subjects whose parents agreed to participate in the study and who had read, understood, and signed a written informed consent form were enrolled. An assent was taken from subjects older than 7 years and an informed consent was signed by the parents. A detailed history was obtained through a self-administered questionnaire derived from the ROME IV criteria for diagnosis of infantile colic.^[1] The questions were designed to collect responses of parents to whether the child cried/fussed excessively or inconsolably during the first 5 months after birth, whether the crying was of prolonged duration (≥ 3 hours/day), and whether it affected daily activities of parents or required doctor consultation. Information on management strategies or prescribed medications was also collected. Parents were asked whether the child had poor weight gain in the first five months and whether the crying resolved after 6 months. Binary responses to these questions were collected as a yes/no reply. Finally, history of any of the four disorders (covered as cases in the study) in the family, if any, was recorded. In order to identify possible independent risk factors of infantile colic, information was obtained on gestational age (< 37 weeks or ≥ 37 weeks), type of delivery (normal or C-section), type of feed (breast milk, formula feed, or mixed), and whether the child had low birth weight (< 2.5 kg). The subjects were categorized as those with or without history of infantile colic based on responses of parents (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Study Design

A sample size of 150 (75 cases and 75 controls) was estimated to be sufficient to detect an OR of 2.6, assuming the percentage of participants with infantile colic among controls is 27% with 80% power and 5% level of significance. 25 controls were added to accommodate unplanned matching. As the prevalence of the diseases considered in the four case groups is known to be similar, 75 cases of each disease were collected and compared to the same set of 100 controls. Therefore, the total sample size for the study was 400.

Quantitative variables were described and categorized according to their distribution in the study population. Descriptive analysis to address each covariate for the entire population was performed. Study participants' presence of the diseases and absence of the diseases has been classified as cases and controls and then compared. Mixed effects logistic univariate and multivariate regression modelling was applied to assess factors associated with infantile colic. Shapiro-Wilk test was conducted to check for normality. For p-value analysis, Wilcoxon test was performed for continuous data (since data was skewed) and Pearson's Chi-squared test was used for categorical data.

RESULTS

A total of 300 subjects were enrolled as cases (75 subjects in each case group) and 100 subjects were enrolled as controls (Figure 2). Demographic characteristics of participants including gender, age, weight, height, and weight at birth were recorded; additionally, characteristics that may have an impact on the disease association being studied or on the gut microbiome (for instance, gestational age, type of delivery, type of feed, and family history of the four disorders) were summarized (Table 1). Overall demographic profile was similar between cases and controls, except for a few parameters. As compared to the control group, significant differences were noted in the childhood migraine group with respect to height ($p = 0.0011$), weight ($p = 0.0104$), and gender ($p = 0.0080$), in the allergic rhinitis group with respect to type of feed ($p = 0.0076$) and gender ($p = 0.0071$), in the atopic dermatitis case groups

with respect to weight ($p = 0.045$) and gender ($p = 0.0053$), and in the FAP-NOS group with respect to gender ($p = 0.0093$). Also, family history was significantly different between each case group and the control group as none of the 100 subjects enrolled as controls reported family history of any of the four illnesses ($p < 0.05$ in all cases).

Univariate logistic regression analysis showed a significant association between the control group and cases, when both had a history of infantile colic (OR = 2.94, 95% CI [1.55, 6.08], $p = 0.0017$). Additionally, significant association between infantile colic and each of the four disorders was also observed based on unadjusted odds ratio: allergic rhinitis (OR = 3.14, 95% CI [1.43, 7.24], $p = 0.0052$) and atopic dermatitis (OR = 3.14, 95% CI [1.43, 7.24], $p = 0.005$) were found to have a stronger association with infantile colic as compared to childhood migraine (OR = 2.94, 95% CI [1.33, 6.80], $p = 0.0089$) and FAP-NOS (OR = 2.55, 95% CI [1.13, 5.96], $p = 0.025$) (Table 2, Figure 3). Similar results were obtained using adjusted odds ratio (Table 2, Figure 4).

Figure 2: Participant Disposition.

Figure 3: Unadjusted Measures of Association: Case Vs. Control.

Figure 4: Adjusted Measures of Association: Case Vs. Control.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Study Participants

Parameter	Allergic rhinitis (N = 75)	Atopic dermatitis (N = 75)	Childhood migraine (N = 75)	Functional abdominal pain-not otherwise specified (FAP-NOS) (N = 75)	Control (N = 100)
Age (years)					
Mean (SD)	8.30 (4.16)	6.41 (3.81)	9.83 (3.32)	7.94 (3.23)	7.91 (4.05)
Median (min, max)	7.58 (2.35, 18.82)	5.54 (2.00, 18.32)	9.27 (4.57, 17.90)	7.97 (2.24, 16.74)	8.21 (2.15, 16.30)
Height (cm)					
Mean (SD)	124.8 (24.11)	112.2 (24.14)	131.7 (17.15)	122.5 (19.00)	119.15 (26.10)
Median (min, max)	122.5 (80.5, 180.0)	106.5 (60.0, 167.0)	133.2 (85.0, 165.0)	126.0 (79.0, 163.0)	115.00 (57.00, 180.40)
Weight (kg)					
Mean (SD)	29.23 (15.24)	22.9 (12.55)	31.15 (11.52)	26.12 (9.94)	27.77 (15.35)
Median (min, max)	24.50 (10.00, 74.00)	19.4 (9.0, 65.0)	30.00 (15.00, 75.00)	26.00 (8.00, 51.90)	24.80 (10.00, 91.00)
Gestational age (weeks)					

Parameter	Allergic rhinitis (N = 75)	Atopic dermatitis (N = 75)	Childhood migraine (N = 75)	Functional abdominal pain-not otherwise specified (FAP-NOS) (N = 75)	Control (N = 100)
Mean (SD)	37.79 (1.20)	37.65 (1.58)	37.95 (1.16)	37.88 (1.11)	37.62 (1.17)
Median (min, max)	38.00 (35.00, 40.00)	38.00 (35.00, 49.00)	38.00 (36.00, 42.00)	38.00 (34.00, 40.00)	38.00 (34.00, 42.00)
Birth weight (kg)					
Mean (SD)	2.88 (0.39)	3.13 (2.46)	2.85 (0.30)	3.26 (3.84)	3.357 (3.56)
Median (min, max)	2.80 (1.60, 3.75)	2.80 (2.100, 24.000)	2.90 (2.00, 3.50)	2.80 (1.95, 36.00)	2.800 (1.650, 30.000)
Type of feed, n*					
Breastfed	54	57	68	54	81
Formula-fed	3	2	4	1	1
Mixed	18	16	3	20	18
Type of delivery, n*					
C-Section	42	37	32	53	41
Normal	33	38	43	22	59
Gender, n*					
Female	29	31	38	38	42
Male	46	44	37	37	58
Family history of the disorder, n*					
Yes	27	15	14	23	0
No	48	60	61	52	100

*n: Number of participants

Table 2: Measures of Association of Cases vs Controls (Unadjusted and Adjusted Odds Ratio).

Disorder	Unadjusted Odds Ratio	95% CI, p-value	Adjusted Odds Ratio	95% CI, p-value	Significant covariates
Allergic rhinitis	3.14	(1.43, 7.24), 0.0052**	3.14	(1.43, 7.24), 0.0052**	None
Atopic dermatitis	3.14	(1.43, 7.24), 0.005**	3.14	(1.43, 7.24), 0.005**	None
Childhood migraine	2.94	(1.33, 6.80), 0.0089**	2.81	(1.25, 6.65), 0.014*	Type of feed
Functional abdominal pain-not otherwise specified (FAP-NOS)	2.55	(1.13, 5.96), 0.025**	2.92	(1.24, 7.18), 0.015*	Type of delivery

*: $p < 0.05$; **: $p < 0.01$

Analysis was done to identify independent risk factors affecting the association of infantile colic with subsequent development of other disorders. In univariate analysis, Gestational age <37 weeks was identified as an independent risk factor in the association of infantile colic with atopic dermatitis (OR = 16.25, 95% CI [1.91, 366.12], $p = 0.0241$). Similarly, C-section delivery had a significant effect on the association of infantile colic with both allergic rhinitis (OR = 4.49, 95% CI [1.27, 21.17], $p = 0.0305$) as well as childhood migraine (OR = 4.95, 95% CI [1.32, 24.09], $p = 0.0256$). Mixed type of feed significantly affected the association of infantile colic with FAP-NOS (OR = 13.9, 95% CI [2.17, 275.46], $p = 0.0190$). Low birth weight was not found to significantly affect the association of infantile colic with any of the disorders ($p > 0.005$).

Multivariate regression analysis conducted considering each of the four disorders with control as response variable and all other covariates as predictor variables showed significant effect of type of feed on the association of infantile colic with childhood migraine, and type of delivery on the association of infantile colic with FAP-NOS (Table 2); association of atopic dermatitis with infantile colic was not significantly affected by any of the covariates. In case of allergic rhinitis, its association with infantile colic was found to be significantly affected by gestational age in the presence of other covariates such as type of feed, type of delivery, and family history of the participant; however, the effect disappeared when the above-mentioned covariates were removed from the regression model. Type of feed, type of delivery, or family history of the participant individually does not have any significant effect on the association of infantile colic with allergic rhinitis.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This study showed that allergic rhinitis, atopic dermatitis, childhood migraine, and FAP-NOS had a strong association with a history of infantile colic ($p < 0.05$ for each disease); allergic rhinitis (OR = 3.14) and atopic dermatitis (OR = 3.14) was found to have a stronger association with infantile colic compared to childhood migraine (OR = 2.94) and FAP-NOS (OR = 2.55). We went on to check whether there were independent risk factors that affected these associations. Indeed, using univariate analysis, we found that gestational age <37 weeks was an independent risk factor in the association of infantile colic with atopic dermatitis (OR = 16.25), C-section delivery was an independent risk factor in the association of infantile colic with both allergic rhinitis (OR = 4.49) as well as childhood migraine (OR = 4.95), and mixed type of feed (breast milk with formula feed) significantly affected the association of infantile colic with FAP-NOS (OR = 13.9). Low birth weight (<2.5 kg) was not found to significantly affect the association of infantile colic with any of the disorders. Multivariate regression analysis conducted considering all covariates as predictor variables showed that the association of infantile colic with childhood migraine and FAP-NOS was affected by type of feed and type of delivery, respectively.

Earlier studies have demonstrated infantile colic to be associated with not just psychological, behavioral, and developmental disorders^[7,16] but also to childhood disorders. A long-term prospective study revealed an association between infantile colic and susceptibility to recurrent abdominal pain ($p = 0.001$) and allergic disorders like allergic rhinitis, conjunctivitis, asthmatic bronchitis, pollenosis, atopic eczema, and food allergy ($p < 0.05$). Furthermore, colic in infants was found to have a significant association with a family history of gastrointestinal diseases and atopic diseases ($p < 0.05$), thus making the association bidirectional. The authors concluded that infantile colic might be an early expression of common childhood disorders.^[7] Likewise, we also report a significant association of infantile colic with allergic rhinitis (OR = 3.14, $p = 0.0052$), atopic dermatitis (OR = 3.14, $p = 0.005$), and FAP-NOS (OR = 2.55, $p = 0.025$). Infantile colic has also been linked to atopic and allergic disorders. In a prospective follow-up study, it was shown that significantly more children with atopic disease at 2 years of age presented with fussing during infancy.^[5] Frequent wheezing (OR = 3.3, 95%CI [1.5, 7.4]) and asthma (OR = 6.6, 95%CI [1.2, 35.9]) were found to be significantly associated with infantile colic in Italian children.^[6] The OR was found to be 3.14 in the present study for allergic rhinitis/asthma and infantile colic. Minor differences with the value reported in the study by Stazi et al.^[6] might be because of the difference in geographic region, difference in age-group analyzed, or because we have considered allergic rhinitis/asthma together as a group while asthma was analyzed separately in the earlier study. Thus, infantile colic might pose increased risk for subsequent allergic disease or atopy, although conflicting results have been reported in other studies.^[17]

Some earlier studies have also demonstrated an association of infantile colic with childhood migraine. A case control study by Romanello et al. showed that children with migraine were more likely to have a history of infantile colic as compared to those without migraine (72.6% vs 26.5%; OR = 6.61, 95% CI [4.38, 10.00], $p < 0.001$).^[8] A prospective cohort study published in 2015 showed that migraine was present in 23% of adolescents with a history of infantile colic compared to 11% of adolescents with no history of infantile colic.^[9] A retrospective case control study from Iran showed that a higher proportion of children in the migraine group as compared to control group had a history of infantile colic (41.46% versus 35.7%). This study further went on to show that an appreciable number of

participants with infantile colic had a family history of migraine, thus pointing to a significant relation between migraine and colic, based on which the authors speculated a common pathophysiology for both these pain syndromes.^[10] It might be interesting to investigate whether dysbiosis is the elusive link. Gelfand et al. in a systematic review reported an OR for the association between migraine and infant colic as 6.5 (95% CI [4.6, 8.9], $p < 0.001$).^[18] Similar findings were reported in a meta-analysis of 7 studies wherein an OR was found to be 2.51 (95% CI [1.32, 4.77], $p = 0.05$).^[19] This is similar to the present study wherein we report significant association ($p = 0.0089$) of infantile colic with childhood migraine with an OR of 2.94.

Overall, our results show that in the absence of confounding factors, having a history of infantile colic might increase the chances of a child subsequently having allergic rhinitis or atopic dermatitis by 3.14 times, childhood migraine by 2.94 times, and FAP-NOS by 2.55 times. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first case control study in the Indian population to establish the link between infantile colic and childhood diseases and atopic disorders. The study enrolled subjects from four geographically diverse regions in the country accounting for possible dietary variations. The questionnaire used in the study was derived from the ROME IV criteria, which emphasizes on ‘irritability reported by caregivers’ as a diagnostic criterion for infantile colic. However, as is common in case control studies of similar design, the study is limited by a potential recall bias in ascertaining history of colic based on parent response. Nevertheless, we tried our best to include demographically matched controls from similar settings as cases in order to control for possible variations.

Based on our findings, we conclude that there is a significant association between infantile colic and development of childhood functional and atopic disorders namely allergic rhinitis/asthma, atopic dermatitis, migraine, and FAP-NOS. Therefore, effective management of infantile colic might reduce the likelihood and/or severity of childhood disorders. Further studies are, however, required to ascertain this with more confidence.

Funding: Funding for this study was provided by Dr. Reddy’s Laboratories Limited.

Clinical trial registration number: CTRI/2020/10/028445 [Registered on: 16 October 2020]

Acknowledgement: We would like to thank all study subjects and their parents for participating in this study. We would also like to acknowledge the support of Medclin Research in the study conduct. Finally, we would like to thank Abhishek Sharma for helping with statistical analysis.

Author contributions: BCA, BS, SD, SM, PJ, VB, and MM were involved in planning and/or conducting the study and collecting data. MM was involved in data analysis, interpretation, and manuscript preparation. SJ and MS were involved in manuscript preparation. BCA provided critical input for manuscript development. KCV, BK, RR, AGS, SBS, and SVB were involved in funding acquisition. All authors approved the final draft of the manuscript submitted.

Disclosure Statement: KCV, BK, RR, AGS, SBS, and SVB are employees of Dr. Reddy’s Laboratories. The other authors declare no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Ilan J N Koppen, Samuel Nurko, Miguel Saps, Carlo Di Lorenzo, Marc A Benninga. The pediatric Rome IV criteria: what's new?. Expert Rev Gastroenterol Hepatol. 2017;11(3):193-201.
2. Judith Zeevenhooven, Pamela D Browne, Monique P L'Hoir, Carolina de Weerth, Marc A Benninga. Infant colic: mechanisms and management. Nat Rev Gastroenterol Hepatol . 2018;15(8):479-496.
3. J Murugu Sarasu, Manish Narang, Dheeraj Shah. Infantile Colic: An Update. Indian Pediatr. 2018;55(11):979-987.
4. Abdelhalim Ouald Chaib, Elvira Ingrid Levy, Mariam Ouald Chaib, Yvan Vandenplas. The influence of the gastrointestinal microbiome on infant colic. Expert Rev Gastroenterol Hepatol. 2020;14(10):919-932.
5. M Kalliomäki, P Laippala, H Korvenranta, P Kero, E Isolauri. Extent of fussing and colic type crying preceding atopic disease. Arch Dis Child. 2001;84(4):349-50.
6. Maria-Antonietta Stazi, Francesca Sampogna, Giuseppe Montagano, Michele E Grandolfo, Marie-France Couilliot, Isabella Annesi-Maesano. Early life factors related to clinical manifestations of atopic disease but not to skin-prick test positivity in young children. Pediatr Allergy Immunol. 2002;13(2):105-12.
7. F Savino, E Castagno, R Bretto, C Brondello, E Palumeri, R Oggero. A prospective 10-year study on children who had severe infantile colic. Acta Paediatr Suppl. 2005;94(449):129-32.
8. Silvia Romanello, Daniele Spiri, Elena Marcuzzi, Anna Zanin, Priscilla Boizeau, Simon Riviere, et al., Association between childhood migraine and history of infantile colic. JAMA. 2013;309(15):1607-12.
9. M. Sillanpää, M Saarinen. Infantile colic associated with childhood migraine: A prospective cohort study. Cephalalgia. 2015;35(14):1246-51.
10. M Tabrizi, H Badeli, A Hassanzadeh Rad, V Aminzadeh, A Shokuhifard. Is Infantile Colic an Early Life Expression of Childhood Migraine?. Iran J Child Neurol . 2017;11(3):37-41.
11. K. Suklert, N Phavichitr. Incidence and Associated Factors of Infantile Colic in Thai Infants. Pediatr Gastroenterol Hepatol Nutr . 2022;25(3):276-282.
12. SV Kumbhare, DVV. Patangia, RH Patil, YS Shouche, NP Patil. Factors influencing the gut microbiome in children: from infancy to childhood. J Biosci. 2019;44(2):49.
13. J Bousquet, P Van Cauwenberge, N Khaltaev, Aria Workshop Group, and World Health Organization. Allergic rhinitis and its impact on asthma. J Allergy Clin Immunol . 2001;108(5 Suppl):S147-334.
14. Lawrence F Eichenfield, Wynniss L Tom, Sarah L Chamlin, Steven R Feldman, Jon M Hanifin, Eric L Simpson, et al. Guidelines of care for the management of atopic dermatitis: section 1. Diagnosis and assessment of atopic dermatitis. J Am Acad Dermatol. 2014;70(2):338-51.
15. Headache Classification Committee of the International Headache Society (IHS) The International Classification of Headache Disorders, 3rd edition. Cephalalgia. 2018;38(1):1-211.
16. L Valla, MC Småstuen, R Andenæs, N Misvær, C Olbjørn, S Helseth. Association between colic and sleep problems in infancy and subsequent development, emotional and behavioral problems: a longitudinal study. BMC Pediatr. 2021;21:21-23.

17. J A Castro-Rodríguez, D A Stern, M Halonen, A L Wright, C J Holberg, L M Taussig, F D Martinez. Relation between infantile colic and asthma/atopy: a prospective study in an unselected population. Pediatrics. 2001;108(4):878-82.
18. Amy A Gelfand, Peter J Goadsby, I Elaine Allen, The relationship between migraine and infant colic: a systematic review and meta-analysis. Cephalalgia. 2015;35(1):63-72.
19. D Zhang, Y Zhang, Y Sang, N Zheng, X Liu. The Relationship between Infant Colic and Migraine as well as Tension-Type Headache: A Meta-Analysis. Pain Res Manag. 2019; 2019: 8307982.